

MAGNETOMETRIC COMPLEX OF THE GEOMAGNETIC OBSERVATORY "ARGENTINE ISLANDS" OF THE UKRAINIAN ANTARCTIC AKADEMIK VERNADSKY STATION

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Magnetic observatories have been and remain basic elements in the study of the state, age-related and modern changes of the geomagnetic field on the Earth's surface. The results of their work are necessary for solving fundamental and applied problems of geomagnetism: development of analytical models of the module of the geomagnetic field induction vector and its components; magnetic mapping based on ground, surface, aerial, and satellite surveys; study of the nature of the sources of internal and external fields; assessment and forecasting of space weather and the ecological state of the environment; interdisciplinary medical and biological research, etc.

The Ukrainian Antarctic Akademik Vernadsky station (since 1996) is the successor of the British Antarctic Base "Michael Faraday", where the Geomagnetic Observatory "Argentine Islands" (according to the IAGA catalog, its code is AIA) has been organized since 1955 and regular registration of the Earth's magnetic field has begun. Since 2004, the AIA Geomagnetic Observatory has been the base in the Antarctic Peninsula region for the international network INTERMAGNET. Obtaining high-quality data on modular and variational components of the geomagnetic field requires constant improvement and updating of instruments and data processing software. The process of modernization of measuring equipment began in 1998 and continues to the present. A large-scale update of the magnetometric complex of the Geomagnetic Observatory and the methodology for processing the initial data took place in 2023–2024.

At the Geomagnetic Observatory "Argentine Islands", new scalar (GSM 19, GSM-90) and variational (LEMI-025) instruments were put into operation, and the software for generating one-second data in the IAGA-2002 format in accordance with the requirements of INTERMAGNET was improved. As a result of processing data from the updated magnetometric complex and recalculated absolute measurements carried out using the new method, one-second data in the IAGA-2002 format in accordance with the requirements of INTERMAGNET were obtained. This makes it possible to continuously record and send data from the AIA Geomagnetic Observatory even in the event of a failure of the main magnetovariation instrument.

After the modernization, the Geomagnetic Observatory "Argentine Islands" becomes the only one in Antarctica and one of the few in the world that will transmit high-quality one-second data of geomagnetic observations in the new format in accordance with the requirements of INTERMAGNET.